

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE ASSESSMENT OF GRASSLANDS PRODUCTIVITY ON THE NORTHERN SIDE OF THE BIHOR MOUNTAINS

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Abstract

The grasslands from the northern part of the Bihor Mountains are poorly productive due to the massive invasion of the native species *Nardus stricta*, *Vaccinium* sp., *Juncus* sp. and other harmful species. In alliances with degraded *Potentillo-Nardion* grass carpet, 1 t/ha of green mass was evaluated; 7.4 pastoral value and 535 l of cow's milk and in the normal *Cynosurion* alliance, 11.44 t/ha of green mass was evaluated; 60.9 pastoral value and 4870 l/ha, more than nine times more.

Keywords: mountain grasslands, pastoral value assessment, grass production, milk production, Bihor Mountains

INTRODUCTION

The vegetation of the mountain grasslands in our country estimated at over 2 million hectares, located from 400–600 m up to 2544 m on the Moldoveanu Peak in the Făgăraș Mountains, has been studied by numerous researchers (Borza, Boșcaiu, 1965; Anghel et al., 1971; Coldea, 1991; Cristea et al., 2004; Donita et al., 2005; Gafta, Mountford 2008 and many others).

In these synthesis works there are few references to the productivity of permanent grasslands, apart from a few reference works that also presented this economic side without which their management cannot be done (Pușchiu et al., 1956; Pușcaru-Soroceanu, 1963; Bărbulescu, Motcă, 1983; Marușca et al., 2014; Marușca, 2022; and others).

In the present work, the evaluation of the productivity of the mountain grasslands based on the floristic survey according to the new method (Marușca, 2019) for the Western Carpathians in the Apuseni Mountains (Pașcuț, Marușca 2020; Marușca, 2021a, 2021b; Marușca et al., 2021, 2022) continues.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The evaluation of grasslands productivity is based on the floristic surveys of the doctoral thesis entitled "*Flora and vegetation from the northern part of the Bihor Mountains*" drawn up by George-Claudiu Togor under the guidance of Prof. Univ. Petru Burescu, held in 2016 at the University of Oradea.

In this paper, 12 permanent grassland associations belonging to 9 alliances, 7 orders and 4 phytosociological classes are presented.

Overview of plant associations in the northern part of the Bihor Mountains:

Class MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA R. Tüxen 1937

Order POTENTILLO-POLYGONETALIA R. Tüxen 1947

Alliance Juncenenion effusi Westhoff et van Leeuwen ex Hejný et al. 1979

1. *Juncetum effusi* Soó (1931) 1949

Order MOLINIETALIA CAERULEAE Koch 1926

Alliance Molinion caeruleae Koch 1926

2. *Junco-Molinietum* Preising in T. Tx. et Preising ex Klapp 1954

Alliance Calthion palustris R. Tüxen 1937

3. *Ranunculo repentis – Calthetum palustris* Chifu, Mânzu et Zamfirescu 2006

Order ARRHENATHERETALIA R. Tüxen 1931

Alliance Cynosurion R. Tüxen 1947

4. *Festuco rubrae – Agrostietum capillaris* Horvat 1951

5. *Anthyllido vulnerariae – Festucetum rubrae* Soó 1971

Class NARDO – CALLUNETEA Preising 1949

Order NARDETALIA Oberdorfer 1949

Alliance Potentillo – Nardion Simion 1959

6. *Festuco rubrae – Nardetum strictae* Csűrös et Resmeriță 1960

7. *Violo declinatae – Nardetum strictae* Simion 1966

8. *Carici – Nardetum strictae* (Resmeriță 1984) Resmeriță et Pop 1986

Alliance Genistion pilosae Duvigneaud 1942

9. *Vaccinio – Callunetum vulgaris* Bükér 1942

Class FESTUCO – BROMETA Br. – Bl. et R. Tüxen in Br. – Bl. 1949

Order FESTUCETALIA VALESIIACAE Br. – Bl. et R. Tüxen in Br. – Bl. 1949

Alliance Festucion valesiaca Klika 1931

10. *Koelerietum macrantae* (Răvăruiș et al. 1956) Popescu et Sanda 1988

Order STIPIO PULCHERRIMAE – FESTUCELIA PALLENTIS I. Pop 1968

Alliance Seslerio – Festucion pallentis Klika 1931

11. *Asplenio rutae – murariae – Melicetum ciliatae* Soó 1962

Class EPILOBIETEA ANGUSTIFOLII Tüxen et Preising in Tüxen 1950

Order ATROPETALIA Vlieger 1937

Alliance Carici piluliferae – Epilobion angustifolii R. Tüxen 1950

12. *Deschampsietum flexuosae* Issler 1942 emand. Borza 1946

The proper evaluation method based on floristic survey was presented for the Perșani mountains in the article published in "Journal of Montanology" no. 13, pp. 23–32 (Marușca et al., 2020), so it is no longer presented in this paper.

Finally, the evaluation of grasslands productivity through green mass production and pastoral value was complemented by the evaluation of cow milk production in the grazing season based on our own long-term experiments (Maruşca et al., 2018, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before evaluating the grasslands productivity, the main stationary conditions and vegetation covering are presented (Table 1).

The grasslands from the study area are found between 700–1610 m altitude on slopes with mostly sunny exposures and inclinations from " to 40 degrees, exceptionally 70 degrees on the cliffs.

The average number of cormophyte species in the vegetal carpet is 62, with great differences between the 12 vegetal associations, established on the basis of 71 surveys.

Above average, the species richest associations are with 200 species *Festuco rubrae* – *Agrostietum capillaris*, 71 species *Festuco rubrae* – *Nardetum strictae* and 64 species *Asplenio rutae* – *murariae* – *Melicetum ciliatae*.

The fewest species were recorded in the associations *Juncetum effusi* with 34 species, *Carici* – *Nardetum strictae* with 41 species and *Koelerietum macrantae* with 41 species.

Table 1. General data on the location and vegetation of grassland phytocenoses

No.	Grassland associations	Altitude (m)	Exposition	Inclination	Cormophyte	Coverage
Al. <i>Juncenion effusi</i>						
1	<i>Juncetum effusi</i>	770-950	Flat	0	34	91.7
Al. <i>Molinion caeruleae</i>						
2	<i>Junco-Molinietum</i>	1240-1360	Flat	0	49	97.0
Al. <i>Calthion palustris</i>						
3	<i>Ranunculo repentis</i> – <i>Calthetum palustris</i>	800-1300	SW, W, NV	5-10	57	84.0
Al. <i>Cynosurion</i>						
4	<i>Festuco rubrae</i> – <i>Agrostietum capillaris</i>	700-1360	E, S, SE, SW, NW	2-30	200	97.5
5	<i>Anthyllido vulnerariae</i> – <i>Festucetum rubrae</i>	1040	E	10	46	85.0
Al. <i>Potentillo</i> – <i>Nardion</i>						
6	<i>Festuco rubrae</i> – <i>Nardetum strictae</i>	850-1610	E, S, SE, SW, Flat	0-40	71	95.0
7	<i>Violo declinatae</i> – <i>Nardetum strictae</i>	1240-1550	E, SE, SW, W, NW	0-40	59	97.5
8	<i>Carici</i> – <i>Nardetum strictae</i>	1240-1420	Flat, S, SE	0-5	41	80,0

No.	Grassland associations	Altitude (m)	Exposition	Inclination	Cormophyte	Coverage
Al. <i>Genistion pilosae</i>						
9	<i>Vaccinio – Callunetum vulgaris</i>	950–1350	SE, W, SW, S	5–20	45	100.0
Al. <i>Festucion valesiaca</i>						
10	<i>Koelerietum macranta</i>	1220	S	3	41	100.0
Al. <i>Seslerio – Festucion pallentis</i>						
11	<i>Asplenio rutaemurariae – Melicetum ciliatae</i>	780–1100	S, SE	40–70	64	54.2
Al. <i>Carici piluliferae – Epilobion angustifolii</i>						
12	<i>Deschampsietum flexuosae</i>	1400–1480	E, SE	0	40	50
Total-Average		700–1610	All	0–70	62	86.0

The general vegetation cover was 86% with variations from 50% in *Deschampsietum flexuosae* and 80% in *Carici – Nardetum strictae* to 100% in *Vaccinio – Callunetum vulgaris* and *Koelerietum macranta* associations.

In the grass carpet, forage and harmful species participate in different proportions depending on the phytosociological association and alliance (table 2).

With 83% participation of forage species in the grassy carpet are the associations of *Cynosurion* and *Festucion valesiaca* alliances.

The alliances comprising the associations with the highest proportion of species harmful to the grass carpet and animal products, as well as with a high proportion of toxic species, are *Molinion caeruleae* with 94.6%, *Juncenion effusi* with 86% and *Calthion palustris* with 83.5%. To these is added the *Violo declinatae – Nardetum strictae* association with 92.5% coverage of harmful species.

On average, the grasslands from the northern part of the Bihor Mountains are degraded, with only 28.6% participation of forage species and 57.4% of harmful species.

Table 2. Participation of forage species, green mass production and the pastoral value of grassland associations

No.	Grassland associations	Species structure (%)		Green mass production		Pastoral value	
		Forager	Harmful	t/ha	%	ind.	%
Al. <i>Juncenion effusi</i>							
1	<i>Juncetum effusi</i>	5.7	86.0	0.56	19	4.0	21
Al. <i>Molinion caeruleae</i>							
2	<i>Junco-Molinietum</i>	2.4	94.6	0.20	7	1.6	9

No.	Grassland associations	Species structure (%)		Green mass production		Pastoral value	
		Forager	Harmful	t/ha	%	ind.	%
Al. <i>Calthion palustris</i>							
3	<i>Ranunculo repentis – Calthetum palustris</i>	0.5	83.5	0.03	1	0.3	2
Al. <i>Cynosurion</i>							
4	<i>Festuco rubrae – Agrostietum capillaris</i>	88.9	8.6	13.07	439	68.2	363
5	<i>Anthyllido vulnerariae – Festucetum rubrae</i>	77.4	7.6	9.80	329	53.5	285
Al. <i>Potentillo – Nardion</i>							
6	<i>Festuco rubrae – Nardetum strictae</i>	30.4	64.6	2.45	82	17.3	92
7	<i>Violo declinatae – Nardetum strictae</i>	5.0	92.5	0.38	13	3.3	49
8	<i>Carici – Nardetum strictae</i>	2.5	77.5	0.17	6	1.6	9
Al. <i>Genistion pilosae</i>							
9	<i>Vaccinio – Callunetum vulgaris</i>	7.2	92.8	0.36	12	3.4	18
Al. <i>Festucion valesiaca</i>							
10	<i>Koelerietum macrantae</i>	83.0	17.0	6.30	211	47.9	255
Al. <i>Seslerio – Festucion pallentis</i>							
11	<i>Asplenio rutaе – murariae – Melicetum ciliatae</i>	1.0	53.2	0.06	2	0.5	3
Al. <i>Carici piluliferae – Epilobion angustifolii</i>							
12	<i>Deschampsietum flexuosae</i>	30.8	10.5	2.33	78	18.0	96
Total-Average		28.6	57.4	2.98	100	18.8	100

As a result of the low participation of forage species in the grass carpet, the average production of green mass is 2.98 t/ha, with a pastoral value of 18.8, considered poor quality.

The highest productions of green mass are assessed in the associations *Festuco rubrae – Agrostietum capillaris* (13.07 t/ha), *Anthyllido vulnerariae – Festucetum rubrae* (9.8 t/ha) and *Koelerietum macrantae* (6.3 t/ha), having in this order also the highest pastoral values (68.2; 53.5; 47.9) rated as average to good quality.

At the opposite pole are the alliances mentioned before, which have the highest percentages of harmful species with are *Juncenion*, *Molinion*, *Calthion*, *Genistion* to which *Potentillo – Nardion* and *Seslerio – Festucion* are added, which are considered very degraded productively and qualitatively.

For these reasons, in the final synthesis of the grasslands evaluation, these alliances were excluded except for one, *Potentillo – Nardion*, which is more widespread (Table 3).

Table 3. Optimum loading, length of grazing season and cow milk production of the most important phytosociological alliances in grasslands

Alliance	Green mass production		Grazing season (days)	Optimal loading (LU/ha)	Pastoral value (ind.)	Milk production	
	t/ha	%				l/ha	%
<i>Cynosurion</i>	11.44	217	135	1.30	60.9	4870	196
<i>Potentillo – Nardion</i>	1.00	19	115	0.13	7.4	525	21
<i>Festucion valesiaca</i>	6.30	120	120	0.81	47.9	3370	136
<i>Carici piluliferae – Epilobion angustifolii</i>	2.33	44	105	0.34	18.0	1160	47
Total-Average	5.27	100	120	0.65	33,6	2480	100

Phytosociological alliances are closest to the level of Natura 2000 Habitats (Gafta, Mountford, 2008).

The best results in terms of productivity were assessed at the *Cynosurion* alliance with 11.44 t/ha GMP, which allows an optimal load of 1.3 LU/ha in 135 days of the grazing season, with a pastoral value (PV) of 60.9 with which 4870 liters of cow's milk are obtained per hectare.

In a first approximation of the Carpathians Mountain grasslands, the *Cynosurion* alliance assessed 11.24 t/ha of green mass, a pastoral value of 62.4, which allows a loading of 1.15 LU/ha in 150 days average grazing season (Maruşca, 2022).

The weakest results were evaluated in the alliance derived from *Cynosurion* following the invasion with the native species *Nardus stricta*, namely *Potentillo – Nardion*, where 1 t/ha GMP was evaluated, in 1115 days of grazing with 0.13 LU/ha, barely 7, 4 PV and 535 l/ha milk production.

On average in the Carpathians, at the *Potentillo – Nardion* alliance, 1.76 t/ha of green mass was assessed, with 21.6 pastoral value, which allows a load of 0.26 LU/ha in 130 days (Maruşca, 2022).

From these data it follows that the *Cynosurion* alliance in the Bihor Mountains has a productivity very close to the average of the Carpathians, and the *Potentillo – Nardion* alliance is in a much more advanced stage of degradation.

From the other two alliances *Festucion valesiaca* and *Carici piluliferae – Epilobion angustifolii* the results are intermediate, namely: in the first association 3370 l/ha milk and in the second association 1160 l/ha milk.

CONCLUSIONS

The grasslands from the northern part of the Bihor mountains are generally degraded due to the invasion in different proportions of the native species *Nardus stricta*, *Juncus* sp., *Vaccinium* sp. and other harmful species.

The best results were assessed at the *Cynosurion* alliance with 11.44 t/ha GMP; 60.9 PV and 4870 liters of cow's milk per hectare in 135 days of grazing.

The worst results were evaluated at the *Potentillo-Nardion* alliance with 1t/ha GMP, 7.4 PV and 535 l/ha milk in 115 days of grazing.

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